

Feminist Ideas and Social Movements

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Status of the women in the societies has always been a debatable issue as the status accorded to women in the societies has never been at par to the their male counterparts. The conception involving women about their nature and capability has been associated with negativity. This negative conception about the nature and capability of the women under-mined them and became instrumental in putting them at the lower strata of the society. With the passage of time, women across the globe pitched for their equal status and opportunities in the society. Feminist ideas and social movements found their emergence in Great Britain and the United States that encouraged the migration of people and ideas transcending the international boundaries.

Publications of two celebrated works- Mary Wollstonecraft's "A vindication of rights of women (1792) and John Stuart Mill". The subjection of women (1869) advocated the rights of women with full vigour and spirit. These were the early feminists who demanded greater equality for women in public institutions like government and Church, and in family.

The radical feminists, going further, insisted that women's right must include their right over their mind and body. These feminists stressed upon the need of women's higher education.

These ideas were fuelled by the socio-economic cultural transformation taking place in Europe and North America. Their demands of the education were met and enabled the middle class and working class people to make access to it.

Literacy brought a comprehensive change in the minds of the people and changed their ways of perceiving things. This intellectual change is known as Enlightenment.

This Enlightenment challenged the authority of religion and Churches, as the Enlightenment brought rational thinking among people. Following the Glorious Revolution which took place in 1688, more reforms to improve the societal differences were expected. Established monarchies claiming to have received the divine right to rule, were overthrown in united states and France. Similar movements were launched in Europe and Great Britain questioning the legitimacy of monarchical rule, which were subsequently overthrown. For example in Germany it sparked off similar movements for civil, political and economic rights.

Feminism as a political philosophy, is concerned with the understanding based on the gender. It is also associated with analyzing the lives of women and Patriarchal system which is the root cause of women's oppression. Thus during the decade of 60s and 70s, consciousness raising among women was given top priority. This enabled the women to articulate their experiences in groups. Thus it can be said the feminist philosophy is equally concerned with psycho-analysis.

Feminism attempts to find out the solution to gender problems. The issue involving the gendered division in the society and the gender based discrimination, was brought to the fore by Simone de Beauvoir's second sex which was published in 1949. She criticizes the views of philosophers, writers justifying the women's subordination in the society. Even earlier, Mary Wollstone craft in her celebrated work "A vindication of Rights of Women" (1792) and Virginia Woof in her "A Room of one's own" (1929), examined the problems faced by the women.

There were some other philosophers like John Stuart Mill and Fredrich Engels spoke about the women's inequality in the society in "The subjection of Women" (1869) and the

origin of the family (1884) respectively. Highlighting the differences between 'Sex and Gender'. Kate Millet in her "Sexual Politics" (1970) says that sex is a biological phenomenon whereas gender is a social cultural construct.

Summingly speaking, feminism can be best described as a movement focussing on the demands that women must have the access to all the facilities they need for their overall development. It pitches for women's independence and wishes to see them as functioning individuals in their own rights and not merely the supporters to their male counterparts. This sort of awareness boosted their morale and they begun to demand equality in and all fields in general and in social and political fields particular.

Efforts put forth by the women activists helped them materialize the long awaited dream of the right to franchise, thereby achieving the municipal franchise in 1869 and full-fledged right to role in 1870. The same year witnessed the introduction of suffrage bill which was a Sin Qua none for women to ensure their political participation.

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